

Building the Enhanced Control Plane of Next Generation Central Offices

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The aim of this paper is to illustrate the Control Plane functionalities, strategies, and procedures in the Next Generation Central Offices, which are crucial traffic aggregation points close to the subscribers. The Next Generation Central Offices are becoming integral part of the next generation networks and for this reason the management and control of its internal resources is essential. Initially, the paper explains the Next Generation Central Offices system architecture and its placement within an end-to-end network. Then, it details the use cases and their quantitative analysis, taking into consideration a dense urban area in Paris city, for estimating the downlink and uplink throughput and latency related requirements. Based on these estimations, the paper defines the Next Generation Central Office Control Plane requirements, along with its functional architecture and its internal functional blocks, detailing their specific roles and interactions to meet the bandwidth and latency demands. Finally, the paper describes an early software prototype implementation based on ETSI TeraFlow SDN, highlighting the software extensions implemented for the support of the Next Generation Central Office Control Plane functionalities, strategies, and procedures. The paper concludes with the next steps for the future work, consisting of the integration with an actual Next Generation Central Office and a field trial experiment in an end-to-end network.

***Keywords*—Central Office, ETSI TFS, Software Defined Network control plane, Time Sensitive Networking.**

I. INTRODUCTION

Demand for fixed and mobile network capacity is expected to continue its rapid growth in the near future due to the prominence of Over-The-Top (OTT) video streaming services [1] and the huge increase in the number of connected IoT (estimated at a total of ~25B devices in 2030) [2]. Combined with the stricter timeliness requirements imposed by the services classified under the term “Ultra Low Latency Reliable Communications” (URLLC) [3], the current 5G infrastructure will be profoundly impacted by the emergence of new services, especially in the major traffic

aggregation point close to the subscribers, i.e., the Central Office (CO).

Thus, network operators seek to re-architect the CO into a Next Generation Central Office (NGCO) with a highly scalable aggregate capacity starting from 51.2Tbps (considered as the performance pinnacle of current state-of-art electronic switches) relying on an innovative optically switched backplane exploiting novel optical material properties. Moreover, to manage all NGCO resources towards satisfying the before mentioned services in an automatic and seamless way, the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) paradigm is a fundamental enabler in the NGCO operation. Some of the beneficial features brought by SDN into the Control Plane (CP) of the NGCO include automation of management procedures, performance monitoring, resource optimization, load balancing, service degradation predictions, and interoperability of different technologies, leading to overall cost and time savings.

The aim of this paper is first to present the improvements and the qualitative benefits that the NGCO brings to next generation networks (e.g., B5G and 6G) and, based on some usage scenario later described, to highlight the challenges and benefits brought by the NGCO CP.

The first section provides an overview of the NGCO system architecture, along with its internal structure, detailing the internal composition and the supported types of traffic. The second section provides a quantitative analysis about the estimation of network traffic demand in a dense urban area, emphasizing the importance of the NGCO CP and what are the challenges it faces. The following section explains the motivations and the structure of the NGCO CP along with its functional architecture, briefly describing the functional entities is composed of and the relation with the NGCO Data Plane (DP). The paper then reports some initial results based on the software implementation. Finally, it concludes summarizing the content and outlining the future work.

II. THE NGCO SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 (a) depicts the placement of the (NG)CO within the End-to-End (E2E) network architecture. The (NG)CO is an aggregation point connecting the Core Network (CN), Regional Data Centres (DCs) and the Cloud to the different Service Provider (SP) access networks where subscribers are connected to. Fig. 1 (b) depicts the main elements of the NGCO: i) the Uplink switches, ii) the Interface (IF) cards, iii) the reconfigurable Optical Circuit Switched (OCS) backplane, and iv) the Wavelength Selective Switches (WSSs).

Although Uplink switches and IF Cards are legacy CO elements that provide connectivity to the metro network (upstream) and the subscriber (downstream), respectively, they are significantly enhanced in the NGCO to offer Time Sensitive Networking (TSN) features, i.e., time-aware scheduled transmissions, according to the IEEE802.1Qbv specification [4], and traffic class-based flow prioritization. In other terms, the set of the standard produced by the IEEE802.1 working group, aim at providing deterministic, low-latency a high-reliable network communication. In general, the main advantage of supporting the TSN technologies within the NGCO, is helping to satisfy the very strict requirements in terms of strict and deterministic latency.

The proposed system architecture considers, for each (of the two) Uplink Switch, 256 ports towards the metro side and 256 ports towards 32 IF cards facing the access network, while each IF card offers 16 ports towards the Uplink switches (intra-NGCO traffic) and 16 ports towards the access subscribers.

Fig. 1. NGCO placement in an end-to-end network (a) and NGCO system architecture (b)

Assuming an IF card port capacity of 50 Gbps (in preparation for supporting High Speed 50G-PON), results in a downstream capacity of 800 Gbps for each IF card and a total switching capacity of 25.6 Tbps for each Uplink switch.

The reconfigurable OCS consists of several 2x2 low-loss Phase Change Material (PCM) switching devices, configurable through a hardware Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) controller. The possible configuration of a single 2x2 PCM cell is either “straight” or “cross”, allowing to migrate one or more flows from one Uplink switch to

another. The reconfigurable OCS represents one of the innovations brought by the NGCO.

Finally, the WSSs properly guide the network traffic (on a wavelength basis either) to the NGCO itself or to the Express paths (see Fig. 1 (b)) bypassing the NGCO. In the former case, two types of traffic traversing the Uplink Switches, the O-band OCS and the IF Cards are supported, i.e., TSN traffic and Best Effort traffic. In the latter case, the Express traffic (that is URLLC traffic) bypasses the NGCO through the Express Path, allowing for reduced E2E latency.

Compared to the traditional COs, the proposed NGCO architecture offers the following qualitative benefits:

- a highly energy efficient OCS backplane (due to the non-volatile PCM materials in the 2x2 switching units), which can scale arbitrarily high, unfettered by chassis limitations, to support previously unattainable aggregate switching capacities.
- Native support, via TSN-enabled switches and Express paths, for concurrent flows of latency-limited services, which guarantees that QoS requirements are met, thus bringing increased revenue to the involved stakeholders.
- Inherent dynamic reconfigurability (via the SDN-controlled OCS and Northbound application) facilitating load balancing and automated network intelligence at reduced Operational Expenditure (OPEX).

Based on the above system architecture of the NGCO, its overall capacity and the types of traffic supported, the next section quantitatively elaborates on some uses cases and lists their diverse traffic requirements.

III. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF A USE CASE

To quantitatively analyse a Use Case (UC), we first need to identify the current ecosystem of 5G services and solutions. Basically, current 5G applications and UCs can be distinguished into three 5G traffic types/services:

- Enhanced Mobile BroadBand (eMBB), for 5G applications demanding high bandwidth, such as video streaming, video conferencing, Virtual Reality (VR) etc.
- URLLC, for 5G applications requiring reliable and mission critical communication with stringent requirements in terms of reliability, end-to-end latency and so on.
- Massive Machine Type Connectivity (mMTC) services target offering connectivity to a large number of connected devices, in the context of IoT, smart city, smart grid environments etc.

The technical specifications and requirements of the above UC types can be found in the Deliverable D2.1 of the OCTAPUS EU-funded project [5]. Assuming that these services are offered in a dense urban area with high number of active subscribers, we consider the geographical area of two districts in Paris, called “arrondissements” 14 and 15. The area covers around 14.123 km² and contains a population of 366,112 [6] [7]. The amount of network traffic generated depends strongly on people activities during the

day. TABLE I summarizes three different Usage Scenarios (USs), specifically Rush hour (US1) (8 to 9 am), Busy hour (US2) (approximately 12am to 1pm and 7-8 pm) and Night hour (US3) (e.g. 2 to 5 am), in terms of estimates on the population commuting, being at home, and at work in each Usage Scenario.

TABLE I. PERCENTAGE OF POPULATION COMMUTING, AT HOME, AND AT WORK IN THE DIFFERENT USAGE SCENARIOS

US Name	Brief description	Population commuting (%), at home (%) and at work (%)
Rush hour (US1)	Most people are commuting from home to work, normal usage of network service.	50% / 20% / 30%
Busy hour (US2)	During or after working hours.	10% / 20% / 70%
Night hour (US3)	Most people are at home asleep.	5% / 92% / 3%

Moreover, the traffic split among different service types and their respective service requirements can vary significantly among different subscriber types (e.g., residential, small office, large business, etc.). For each usage scenario, TABLE II summarizes the estimated aggregate data rate requirements in Downlink (DL) and Uplink (UL), along with the estimated latency, for the traffic that must be served by the NGCOs within this area.

The traffic demand within each US varies according to people’s activities: it can be considered as “normal” in US1 (acting as the baseline scenario), while it increases during US2 and is “low” during US3. For what concerns the end-to-end latency range, this is determined by the specific service required (and not by the number of subscribers per se) and it varies a lot, from 0.1 ms to 100 ms.

TABLE II. ESTIMATION OF DATA RATE AND LATENCY RANGE IN USAGE SCENARIOS

US Name	Estimated Total Data Rate in DL and UL (Tbps)	Estimated latency range
Rush hour (US1)	16.8 Tbps in DL; 49.3 Tbps in UL	0.1 to 100 ms
Busy hour (US2)	75.7 Tbps in DL; 116.7 Tbps in UL	0.1 to 100 ms
Night hour (US3)	4.2 Tbps in DL; 3.9 Tbps in UL	0.1 to 100 ms

This large range of the estimated data rate (in DL and UL) and latency requirements necessitates the management and continuous monitoring of status of the different services, as they are served by four NGCOs (considering the most demanding Busy hour US2 and assuming an aggregate capacity of 51.2 Tbps per NGCO), to prevent and avoid possible service degradation. Moreover, depending on the service required, it can be mapped in one of the three types of traffic, i.e., Best Effort for the “common” traffic, TSN traffic for strict latency-oriented services and, finally, Express traffic for either more stringent latency service requirement.

The high dynamicity of the traffic during the different USs, along with their estimated data rate and latency requirements and the diverse type of services that can be potentially included in such USs (e.g. time-sensitive services,

bandwidth-hungry applications and so on), drives the design and development of the CP of the NGCO.

Based on these identified requirements and the internal structure of the NGCO, the functional architecture of the NGCO CP is defined in the next section.

IV. NGCO CONTROL PLANE

A. Requirements and Functional Architecture

Given the large range of the estimated requirements in terms of data rate and latency within the USs, the NGCO CP must at least satisfy the following qualitative operational requirements:

- NGCO DP information management, i.e., retrieving and managing information about the NGCO itself.
- NGCO topology and flow abstraction, consisting of managing and simplifying the complexity of the technology implemented by the NGCO.
- NGCO flow lifecycle management, for managing the three types of traffic identified in a seamless way.
- Interoperability of the TSN and the optical technologies encompassed in the OCS backplane.
- NGCO performance monitoring, for continuously assessing the status of the different flows and possibly applying re-routing or load-balancing actions to prevent service degradation or perform service recovery.

Fig. 2 depicts the functional architecture of the NGCO CP, along with the main interactions with the NGCO DP elements.

Fig. 2. Functional Architecture of NGCO Control Plane

From the CP perspective, the NGCO can be considered as a hybrid network, composed of the TSN devices (i.e., Uplink switches plus the IF cards) and optical devices (i.e., the O-band OCS), respectively.

For this reason, a hierarchical CP structure has been designed: on the lower side of the NGCO CP, the OCS SDN Controller and OCS SDN Agent take care of the management and control of the O-band OCS while the Central Network Controller (CNC), along with the Centralized User Configuration (CUC), constitute the CP of the TSN network comprising the Uplink switches and IF cards. The SDN Coordinator is introduced to manage the entire NGCO CP, interacting with the optical and TSN

Controllers From a functional perspective, the SDN Coordinator collects, manages, and processes the information coming from both domains, specifically from the two Controllers (i.e., OCS SDN and TSN CNC).

B. Optical Control Plane

Briefly, the CP of the O-band OCS consists of the OCS SDN Agent responsible for configuring the PCMs within the O-band OCS, with the aim of forwarding the traffic to either a different Uplink switch or IF card. Moreover, the OCS SDN Agent can monitor the status of the O-band OCS and its performance to retrieve useful information to provide to the CP upper layers. Indeed, the OCS SDN Controller represents the CP functional entity of the optical network, realizing the following functionalities for the optical network:

- Topology management, which collects connectivity information of the several PCMs within the O-band OCS along with their status.
- Provisioning, for configuring one or more PCMs by setting their proper status (i.e., straight or cross).
- Monitoring, for continuously collecting data about the O-band OCS.
- These functionalities are made available externally to allow control of the O-band OCS.

C. TSN Control Plane

For what concerns the TSN CP, the IEEE802.1Qcc specification defines the procedures and data models for requesting the management of one or more TSN flows in a TSN network [8]. In the fully centralized network model, the CUC collects the requirements from the TSN Talker and Listeners describing the unidirectional, time-constrained TSN flow. In the TSN domain, the Talker and the Listeners refer to the roles of the devices requesting to participate in a time-sensitive communication. Afterwards, the CUC initiates the resource reservation process by communicating with the CNC via the interfaces defined by the IEEE802.1Qdj specification [3]. For these reasons, the CNC and CUC are responsible for the CP of the TSN network. The CNC provides the following functionalities:

- computation of the schedule tables and routes for the individual TSN streams.
- retrieval of the status of the TSN elements.
- scheduling of transmissions at each node, i.e., determining the exact time window where the port of a node is allowed to transmit.

In terms of TSN flow management, the CNC takes as input the TSN traffic properties and requirements provided by the CUC following the IEEE802.1Qdj specification. Then, it processes these requests and translates them into configurations for the network and ports in the TSN domain. In particular, the CNC computes the TSN path from the Talkers to the Listeners, executes the scheduling operation based on the flows requirements and allocates the necessary bandwidth to satisfy the requested QoS. Finally, the CNC requests to the TSN bridges (i.e. the TSN devices to be traversed by the TSN flows from Talker to Listeners) the actual configuration, consisting of routed path configuration

based on VLAN separation and the Gate Control List (GCL) configuration for the reserved TSN resources as per IEEE Std 802.1Qcw [9] specification. Details of VLAN and GCL configuration can be found within the open-source YANG modules, [10] and [11], respectively.

D. The SDN Coordinator

As already mentioned, the SDN Coordinator, interacting with the optical and TSN Controllers is responsible for the NGCO CP and, hence, the management of TSN and non-TSN resources in the hybrid network. The SDN Coordinator can be further decomposed internally in functional blocks, as depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. SDN Coordinator Functional blocks

It shall be noted that all these internal components interact with each other to realize the main CP functionalities, as well as with the SDN Controllers through the Southbound interface (SBI). A brief description of the functional role of each component is provided below:

- The Northbound Interfaces (NBIs) layer represents the entry point for the SDN Coordinator's functionalities. It can be used by external entities, such as a Management System (e.g., a web-based graphical user interface) or by an external orchestrator for the management of end-to-end resources.
- The NGCO Topology manages the DP information of the NGCO itself by collecting, merging, and homogenizing information coming from both TSN and optical domains.
- The NGCO Provisioning is responsible for managing the lifecycle of different types of flows within the NGCO.
- NGCO Monitoring collects metrics from both domains, aggregates them and provides telemetry information related to the NGCO's performance and status.
- The NGCO Re-routing is an internal block that allows the configuration of policies for the automated and closed-loop re-routing of running traffic flows within the NGCO. For instance, if a given threshold is violated for a certain time-window, custom actions (e.g. reduction of allocated resources, service removal) can be applied.
- Even if the CUC belongs to the TSN domain proper, it is included within the SDN Coordinator as an entry point for communicating with the TSN domain, specifically with the CNC.
- The Path Computation Engine (PCE) computes the Explicit Route Object (ERO) from a source to a

destination given a provisioning request and associated constraints.

- Finally, the Southbound Interface (SBI) represents the set of the elements for interacting with both SDN Controllers (optical and TSN).

In conclusion, the SDN Coordinator represents the central entity for the management, control and monitoring of NGCO resources, where the information from the optical and TSN domains are gathered, processed, and homogenized for providing a holistic view about the NGCO.

In the next section, we briefly describe how some of the NGCO CP functional elements have been implemented, starting from the de-facto SDN Controller ETSI TeraFlow SDN (TFS).

E. Early Software implementation

The early software prototype implementation of the NGCO CP is based on the ETSI Teraflow SDN release 2 (TFSr2). Specifically, the SDN Coordinator and the OCS SDN Controller are implemented within TFSr2, while the CNC can be considered as an external TSN Controller to interact with. The TFSr2 is the output of the partially EU-funded project called TeraFlow H2020 [12]. TFSr2 is an open-source, micro-service based and cloud-native SDN Controller whose functional architecture is depicted in Fig. 4.

TFSr2 is formed by different components, with each of them being responsible for a specific task. For instance, the Context component manages the inventory of the SDN Controller, while the Device component manages the connection and the communication with the network devices, implementing the corresponding protocols and so on. The TeraFlow H2020 Deliverable D2.1 [13] and Deliverable D2.2 [14] detail the comprehensive list of the functionalities, UCs and requirements implemented by each of the TFS components.

Fig. 4. TFSr2 Functional Architecture

However, TFSr2 natively does not support the mechanisms for the management, control, and monitoring of the NGCO. From a functional perspective, some of the functional elements of the SDN Coordinator can be easily mapped one-to-one into the existing TFS components (e.g. Monitoring, PCE and Context), while others need one-to-many mapping (NGCO re-routing can be mapped with Policy and Automation and NGCO provisioning and CUC with Slice and Service).

Moreover, TFSr2 does not natively support the data models and workflows of the NGCO CP. For these reasons, software extensions to TFS have been planned and some of them have been implemented to fill these gaps. The planned software extensions include: i) support of the data model for

representing the PCM cells, OCS backplane, and TSN flows, ii) extensions to the Device software component for interacting with the OCS SDN Agent and CNC, iii) support of TSN requirements during the slice provisioning stage request, iv) enhancement of the PCE algorithm to account for potential changes in NGCO topology due to PCM state switching, and v) CUC as a new service handler for managing TSN requests.

One of the extensions is related to the support of latency requirements (i.e., the iii)) during the slice provisioning request stage. As per RFC 9543 [15], “Service Level Objectives (SLOs) define a set of measurable network attributes and characteristics that describe an IETF network Slice Service”. To this end, some of the available SLOs (e.g. one-way-bandwidth, one-way-delay-maximum and one-way-delay-variation-maximum) have been chosen as a baseline for fulfilling the timeliness requirements in the TSN network during the slice provisioning request. These SLOs are properly translated into TSN requirements by the SDN coordinator which, through the CUC, provides them to the CNC as part of the TSN flow. In case that the translation and mapping of a TSN requirement are not possible, then the explicit TSN traffic requirement is provided within the slice provisioning request, specifying the explicit configuration parameter. For the purposes of getting some initial results, the following simulated topology in Fig. 5 resembles a simplified segment of the NGCO DP is taken under consideration.

Fig. 5. Simulated NGCO Topology graphical representation

Starting from the right are represented: a TSN Talker (on the access network side) represented by the outgoing arrow, two Uplink switches, three PCMs, two IF cards, and a Listener (on the metro network side) represented by the incoming arrow. The simulated NGCO topology serves as baseline for a Transport Network (TN) Slice provisioning from Talker to Listener. Specifically, the TN Slice contains the previously mentioned SLOs as constraints. Fig. 6 depicts the TN slice provisioned on the simulated NGCO topology, with the mentioned TSN requirements as SLOs (Fig. 6 (a)), custom TSN requirements (Fig. 6 (b)), with the corresponding shortest path computed (Fig. 6 (c)).

Type	(a)	Value
service-slo-one-way-delay		"1 ms"
service-slo-one-way-delay-variation		"100 us"
service-slo-availability		"99.9"
Path (b)		
TSN-Listener	US1	US1
00:00:00:00:00:30	00:00:00:00:00:04	00:00:00:00:00:01
		2/1
PCM1	IFCARD1	IFCARD1
00:00:00:00:00:20	00:00:00:00:00:1F	00:80:D0:63:C2:26
1/1		
Value (c)		
		• emergency_traffic: False
		• VLAN_tag: 1234
		• eCPRI_stream_period_us: 9
		• max_frame_size: 8000

Fig. 6. Information about TN slice provisioned

It shall be noted that the NGCO provisioning through the CNC can configure the simulated TSN devices properly setting the corresponding configurations. Fig. 7 depicts a CNC TSN-enabled device interface configuration example, relying on the IEEE802.1Qcw specification. A periodic time window of 100 microseconds (green box) is allocated for the Gate Control (GC) entries (blue boxes), configured for non-TSN (127 value) and TSN (128 value) traffic as follow: 10 microseconds for non-TSN traffic, 15 microseconds for guard band traffic (value 0), 45 microseconds for TSN traffic and finally the last 30 not allocated microseconds for non-TSN traffic. The values in the XML are expressed in nanoseconds and the gate-states-value in GC entry refers to the next GC entry rather than the GC entry it belongs to.

Fig. 7. Configuration example of GC entries allocation

To conclude, the TN slice is mapped as a TSN flow within the simulated NGCO. Currently, further software developments are carried out for implementing the functional elements of the NGCO CP. For the NGCO DP, advancements on the prototyping and the integration of the its elements of the NGCO are ongoing.

F. Conclusion and future work

This paper has provided a quantitative study of the service usage scenarios in a dense urban area in Paris, along with an estimation on service demands, in terms of bandwidth and latency (especially in the light of new latency-constrained applications targeted in B5G and 6G networks), by the subscribers living in that area on different USs. Based on these demands, the paper has explained the need for upgrading the current COs' capabilities in future communication networks, towards more automated and intelligent NGCOs, and underlined the motivation and requirements of a hierarchical CP of the NGCO, detailing the internal functional blocks and their roles for managing, controlling, and monitoring it. The paper also reported an early implementation work on the NGCO CP, based on

TFSr2, describing how a TN slice can be provisioned within the NGCO as a TSN flow. Further software and hardware developments and integrations are planned in the future, aiming at a complete integration of the NGCO CP and DP. Finally, a field trial demonstration will be carried out to integrate the NGCO CP with the NGCO DP and showcase support of real-time services with interoperable equipment in an E2E network.

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